

FAM (Finding, Analyzing and Monitoring) Method

Objective: - To find the **COVID-19 Positive Patient** and to provide with a **Swadeshi NavIC** enabled **tracker band** and track his activity like a “**House arrest ankle monitor**” provided by the FBI in USA.

Approach: - We have to prepare teams of workers that will be well equipped with proper protection and sanitization to do a door to door and person to person test in India and if found positive then we have to provide the patient with a wearable NavIC trackers that will send their location to the servers monitored by the authorities.

The trackers will be designed in following manner just as the FBI House Arrest Ankle Monitor provided in USA that:-

- 1) If the band is tried to remove it will switch off.
- 2) If the patient goes out it will send the route of the patient.
- 3) The person has to charge the band on his responsibility

In the above cases the authorities can notify/inform the local authorities to actions in order to detain the patient.

In this case the patient can be quarantined in their house if they have separate rooms with proper preventive measures by the family and person incapable of self-quarantining themselves can be quarantined in hospitals to decrease the load on medical authorities.

If we are able to survey areas to areas, district to district and state to state and once the survey is completed the Authorities can **update** the **Arogya Setu App** with **data** with just the code provided to the patient in order to discrete the identity of patient in order to letting the unaffected people to stay away from patient and areas where not to go and continue their work.

We must install social gathering places like offices, factories, malls, traffic signals with thermal scanning systems and sanitization tunnels to ensure no Corona patient and if found must be contained. We can make this process faster by enrolling Police, NCC, NSS and Scout Volunteers and Army if necessary to make this process faster and patient's family members must send their medical observation like symptoms and temperature readings to the local police station.

If data is submitted Nation-Wide we can relax the lockdown in preventive measures after two weeks of data submission and even if the lockdown persist we will be able to provide medical attention who require it the most and patients still can work from home as well.

Once the patient gets recover he must contact the police station in order to collect the NavIC band and with proper sanitization the band's electronic component can be recycled or reused again.

Conclusion: - **As we cannot wait for vaccine to continue our work it's better to continue the lockdown for COVID-19 positive patients and to collect data for better implementation of policies by government.**

Basic overview of a tracker band(can be changed according to conditions of compatibility)

Basic Idea of NavIC Tracker(can be changed according to conditions of compatibility)

The Power Supply will be connections will be in such a manner that the connections will run through the band, so that if removed by cutting or simple removing will turn the complete module off and stop sending signals which will be notified by authorities.